

Effectiveness of Ice Pack Therapy on the Level of Pain at the Site of Arteriovenous Fistula among Patients Undergoing Hemodialysis at Selected Hemodialysis Centers

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ABSTRACT: -

Hemodialysis requires repeated puncture of the arteriovenous fistula, which often causes moderate to severe pain and discomfort. Persistent pain reduces patient satisfaction, increases anxiety, and may affect adherence to dialysis therapy. Pharmacological methods are not always feasible due to cost, side effects, or availability. Non-pharmacological methods such as ice pack therapy provide a simple and safe alternative. This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of ice pack therapy on reducing puncture pain among hemodialysis patients with AV fistula.

METHOD: - Used quantitative research approach. True experimental post test only research design was used. 60 samples was selected using a non- probability convenient sampling technique 30 for experimental group and 30 for control group. The accessible population consisted of patients having AVF and undergoing hemodialysis. As a intervention apply ice pack on fistula for 10 minutes, five minutes before puncturing the AVF.

Results

The demographic characteristics of both groups were comparable with no significant differences in age, gender, or duration of dialysis. The mean pain score in the experimental group (2.4 ± 0.8) was significantly lower than in the control group (5.6 ± 1.2). Z-test results

showed $p < 0.001$, indicating strong statistical significance. Thus, ice pack therapy effectively reduced puncture-related pain among hemodialysis patients.

Conclusion

Ice pack therapy is a safe, effective, and low-cost intervention to alleviate puncture-related pain in hemodialysis patients. Its adoption in clinical practice can improve patient comfort and satisfaction with dialysis treatment.

KEYWORDS: Ice pack therapy, Arteriovenous Fistula, Hemodialysis, Hemodialysis center.

INTRODUCTION

The kidneys help remove waste products from the body, maintain electrolyte levels, and regulate blood pressure. The kidneys remove various waste products and eliminate them in the urine. The kidney is an important organ, yet most people know little about its crucial role in the body. Consequently, we unknowingly distress this vital organ, mainly through poor lifestyle habits and choices. These two powerful organs work continuously, ridding the body of harmful toxins. They are unbelievably important, and if they become damaged or diseased, life will change significantly.[1] Recent statistics indicate that renal failure is increasing. The incidence of kidney failure (or Chronic Kidney Disease) has doubled in the last 15 years. Dialysis is a technique performed for those patients whose kidneys are not functioning adequately. With renal failure, the kidneys are unable to adequately filter blood.[2] Hemodialysis (HD) is the most common procedure used among other extra-renal purification techniques. Arteriovenous (AV) fistulas are vital conduits for hemodialysis in end-stage renal disease (ESRD) patients, serving as the preferred vascular access due to their durability and lower risk of complications compared to the other access types.[3] Ice application is the simplest and oldest way to treat injuries. Its worldwide use spread because of its effectiveness, convenience, low cost and ease of transportation. Ice is believed to control pain by instigating local anaesthesia. It also decreases oedema, nerve conduction velocities, cellular metabolism and local blood flow.[4]

METHODS:

Study Design: The investigator utilized a True experimental post test only research design. [5]

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.[6]

Setting: Selected hemodialysis centers of the city

Sampling Technique: Non probability, convenient sampling technique.[7]

Population: Patients undergoing hemodialysis.[8]

Study Protocol: The data was collected from 25/12/2024 to 20/01/2025. Before the data collection consent was taken from the participants. The investigator explained everything about the ice pack therapy (definition, benefits, precautions and procedure of Ice pack therapy) to the experimental group. An ice pack was kept in a refrigerator for one hour and taken exactly before applying to the patient. Then an Ice pack was applied at the site of the AV fistula for 10 minutes before 5 minutes of puncturing the fistula in the experimental group and routine care was given to the control group. After the end of the intervention post-test the level of pain was assessed by using the standardized pain scale of both experimental and control groups.

Method of data collection:

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct research.
2. Explain the purpose of the research to the participants.
3. Obtain informed consent (written) from the participants.
4. Ice pack therapy on the experimental group before puncturing of AV fistula.
5. Document the post-intervention effect of ice pack therapy in the experimental group participants.
6. Assess the level of pain of the control group.

The data gathering process began from 25/12/2023 to 20/01/2024. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. The investigator introduced themselves and informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better cooperation during the data collection. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data were discussed. Each subject was given a prepared tool containing.

Section A - Consent form.

Section B - Tool for demographic variable.

Section C - Numerical Rating Pain Scale

Statistical Methods:

The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Two sample z-tests for the comparison of average pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in experimental and control groups and Fisher's exact test for the association between pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis and with demographical variables in the experimental group.

Data Analysis:

Sample Size: The formula used for sample size is-

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2} * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

n = sample size

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ = Critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$

MOE = Margin of error

P = Sample Proportion For calculations, $Z_{\alpha/2}=1.96$

P = 0.34

MOE = 0.125

$$n = 3.84 * 0.34 * 0.66 / 0.0156 \quad n = 0.8616 / 0.0156 \quad n = 55.25$$

The sample size, n comes to be 55. I selected 60 samples. 30 for experimental and 30 for control group.

Sampling Criteria:[9]

a. Inclusive criteria -: Patients who are

- willing to participate in the study
- more than 18 years up to 66 years
- stable on hemodialysis
- undergone more than 1 hemodialysis session
- able to understand Marathi and English language
- having Arteriovenous fistula

b. exclusive criteria-: Patients who are

- unstable on dialysis
- not on any analgesics

c. Withdrawal criteria:

- Sample can withdraw from research at any point of time during the data collection.

Result :

a. Demographic characteristics of patients:

Age:

In the experimental group, 16.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis had aged 18-30 years, 23.3% of them had aged 30.1-42 years, 33.3% of them had aged 42.1-54 years and 26.7% of them had aged 54.1-66 years. In the control group, 16.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis were aged 18-30 years, 26.7% of them had aged 30.1-42 years, 40% of them had aged 42.1-54 years and 16.7% of them had aged 54.1-66 years.

Gender:

In the experimental and control groups, 63.3% of them were males and 36.7% of them were females.

Education:

In experimental group, 30% of them did not have formal education, 33.3% of them had primary education and 36.7% of them had higher secondary education. In control group, 20% of them did not have formal education, 23.3% of them had primary education, 50% of them had higher secondary education and 6.7% of them had graduation.

Occupation:

In the experimental group, 13.3% of them had a business, 23.3% of them had private

jobs, 33.3% of them were homemakers, 13.3% of them were labourers/daily wagers and 16.7% of them were unemployed. In the control group, 23.3% of them had business, 26.7% of them had private jobs, 3.3% of them had government jobs, 30% of them were homemakers, 10% of them were labourers/daily wagers and 6.7% of them were unemployed.

Personal habits:

In the experimental group, 30% of them were alcoholic, 13.3% of them had a habit of cigarette smoking, 23.3% of them had a habit of chewing tobacco and 33.3% of them had some other habit. In the control group, 30% of them were alcoholic, 6.7% of them had a habit of cigarette smoking, 40% of them had a habit of chewing tobacco and 23.3% of them had some other habit.

Diagnosis:

In the experimental and control groups, all of them had chronic kidney disease.

Duration of kidney disease:

In experimental group, 10% of them had kidney disease for less than 3 years, 50% of them had kidney disease for 3-5 years and 40% of them had kidney disease for more than 5 years. In control group, 20% of them had kidney disease for less than 3 years, 43.3% of them had kidney disease for 3- 5 years and 36.7% of them had kidney disease for more than 5 years.

Duration of AV fistula:

In the experimental group, 16.7% of them had a fistula for less than 3 years, 46.7% of them had a fistula for 3-5 years and 36.7% of them had a fistula for more than 5 years. In control group, 30% of them had a fistula for less than 3 years, 36.7% of them had a fistula for 3-5 years and 33.3% of them had a fistula for more than 5 years.

Objective 1: To assess the level of pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing after Ice pack therapy among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hemodialysis centers.

In the experimental group, 76.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis had mild pain and 23.3% of them had moderate pain at the time of fistula. In the control group, 10% of them had moderate pain and 90% of them had severe pain at the time of fistula. This indicates that there is remarkably less pain among patients undergoing hemodialysis after the use of the ice pack therapy.

Two sample z-tests for the comparison of average pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in experimental and control group

The researcher applied two- sample z-test for the comparison of average pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in the experimental and control groups. The average pain score in the experimental group was 3.1 which was 7.3 in the control group. The Z- value for this test was 26.3. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average pain score among patients undergoing hemodialysis in the experimental group is significantly less than that in the control group. It is evident that the use of ice pack therapy is significantly effective in reducing pain among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

Objective 2: To find out the association between the pre-intervention study findings with demographical variables.

Fisher's exact test for the association between pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis and with demographical variables in experimental group.

p-values corresponding to gender and occupation were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables gender and occupation were found to have significant association with the pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in experimental group.

Fisher's exact test for the association between pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis and with demographical variables in control group.

all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in control group.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

On the basis of the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.

1. A similar study may be replicated on large samples thereby findings can be generalized.
2. The study can be replicated in different settings.
3. The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study.
4. A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.
5. Explore with use of different cryotherapy modalities such as ice water immersion or specializes cryotherapy devices.
6. Evaluate the long-term effects of regular ice pack therapy on arteriovenous fistula puncturing pain.
7. Investigate the effectiveness of ice pack therapy in combination with other non- pharmacological interventions such as, relaxation technique, topical analgesics or Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation.

ABBREVIATIONS:

AVF	ArterioVenousFistula
HD	Hemodialysis
ESRD	End Stage Renal Disease
CKD	Chronic Kidney Disease
CVI	Content Validity Index
PD	Peritoneal Dialysis

Table 1: Description of samples (patients undergoing hemodialysis) based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage**n=30, 30**

Demographic variable	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Age				
18-30 years	5	16.7%	5	16.7%
30.1-42 years	7	23.3%	8	26.7%
42.1-54 years	10	33.3%	12	40.0%
54.1-66 years	8	26.7%	5	16.7%
Sex				
Male	19	63.3%	19	63.3%
Female	11	36.7%	11	36.7%
Transgender	0	0%	0	0%
Not to be specified	0	0%	0	0%
Education				
No formal education	9	30.0%	6	20.0%
Primary	10	33.3%	7	23.3%
Higher secondary	11	36.7%	15	50.0%
Graduation	0	0.0%	2	6.7%
Occupation				
Business	4	13.3%	7	23.3%
Private job	7	23.3%	8	26.7%
Government job	0	0.0%	1	3.3%
Homemaker	10	33.3%	9	30.0%
Labourer /daily wager	4	13.3%	3	10.0%
Unemployed	5	16.7%	2	6.7%
Personal habits				
Alcoholic	9	30.0%	9	30.0%
Cigarette smoker	4	13.3%	2	6.7%
Tobacco chewing	7	23.3%	12	40.0%
Others	10	33.3%	7	23.3%

Diagnosis				
Acute kidney failure	0	0	0	0
Chronic kidney failure	30	100.0%	30	100.0%
Duration of kidney disease				
Less than 3 years	3	10.0%	6	20.0%
3- 5 years	15	50.0%	13	43.3%
More than 5 years	12	40.0%	11	36.7%
Duration of Fistula				
Less than 3 years	5	16.7%	9	30.0%
3-5 years	14	46.7%	11	36.7%
More than 5 years	11	36.7%	10	33.3%

Table 2: Level of pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing after Ice pack therapy among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hemodialysis centers

n=30, 30

Pain at the time of fistula	Experimental		Control	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
None	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	23	76.7%	0	0.0%
Moderate	7	23.3%	3	10.0%
Severe	0	0.0%	27	90.0%

Table 3: Two sample z-test for the comparison of average pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in experimental and control group

n=30, 30

Group	Mean	SD	z	p-value
Experimental	3.1	0.6	26.3	0.000
Control	7.3	0.7		

Figure no. 1 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to age.)

In the experimental group, 16.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis had age 18-30 years, 23.3% of them had age 30.1-42 years, 33.3% of them had age 42.1-54 years and 26.7% of them had age 54.1-66 years. In control group, 16.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis had age 18-30 years, 26.7% of them had age 30.1-42 years, 40% of them had age 42.1-54 years and 16.7% of them had age 54.1-66 years.

Figure no. 2 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to gender.)

In the experimental and the control groups, 63.3% of them were males and 36.7% of them were females.

Figure no. 3 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to education.)

In the experimental group, 30% of them did not have formal education, 33.3% of them had primary education and 36.7% of them had higher secondary education. In the control group, 20% of them did not have formal education, 23.3% of them had primary education, 50% of them had higher secondary education and 6.7% of them had graduation.

Figure no.4 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to occupation.)

In the experimental group, 13.3% of them had business, 23.3% of them had private job, 33.3% of them were homemakers, 13.3% of them were labourers/daily wagers and 16.7% of them were unemployed. In control group, 23.3% of them had business, 26.7% of them had private job, 3.3% of them had government job, 30% of them were homemakers, 10% of them were labourers/daily wagers and 6.7% of them were unemployed.

Figure no.5 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to personal habits)

In the experimental group, 30% of them were alcoholic, 13.3% of them had habit of cigarette smoking, 23.3% of them had habit of chewing tobacco and 33.3% of them had some other habit. In the control group, 30% of them were alcoholic, 6.7% of them had habit of cigarette smoking, 40% of them had habit of chewing tobacco and 23.3% of them had some other habit.

Figure no. 6 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to diagnosis.)

In the experimental and the control group, all of them had chronic kidney disease.

Figure no 7 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to duration of kidney disease.)

In the experimental group, 10% of them had kidney disease for less than 3 years, 50% of them had kidney disease for 3-5 years and 40% of them had kidney disease for more than 5 years. In the control group, 20% of them had kidney disease for less than 3 years, 43.3% of them had kidney disease for 3-5 years and 36.7% of them had kidney disease for more than 5 years

Figure no.8 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to duration of AV Fistula.)

In the experimental group, 16.7% of them had fistula for less than 3 years, 46.7% of them had fistula for 3-5 years and 36.7% of them had fistula for more than 5 years. In the control group, 30% of them had fistula for less than 3 years, 36.7% of them had fistula for 3-5 years and 33.3% of them had fistula for more than 5 years.

Figure no.9 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients according to level of pain.)

In the experimental group, 76.7% of the patients undergoing hemodialysis had mild pain and 23.3% of them had moderate pain at the time of fistula. In the control group, 10% of them had moderate pain and 90% of them had severe pain at the time of fistula. This indicates that there is remarkably less pain among patients undergoing hemodialysis after the use of the ice pack therapy.

Figure no. 10 (bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution of patients average pain score.)

The researcher applied two- sample z-test for the comparison of average pain at the time of AV Fistula puncturing among patients undergoing hemodialysis in experimental and control group. The average pain score in the experimental group was 3.1 which was 7.3 in the control group. The Z- value for this test was 26.3. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average pain score among patients undergoing hemodialysis in the experimental group is significantly less than that in the control group. It is evident that the use of ice pack therapy is significantly effective in reducing pain among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

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